

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ETHNIC DISTANCE AS A FACTOR HINDERING THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHINESE-JAPANESE RELATIONS (BASED ON THE ACTIVITIES OF UNIT 731)

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Abstract

World War II is a global catastrophe for humanity. The consequences of this event left their mark on citizens of different countries. The authors studied the "ethnic distance" of the Chinese and Japanese ethnic groups against the backdrop of World War II. It was determined that the main factor influencing the existing "post-conflict anxieties" of the Chinese is associated with the brutal research programs of the Japanese army, namely the activities of Unit 731 in China. The authors of the article are inclined to believe that Sino-Japanese relations will not be able to have positive dynamics due to the psychological mentality of Chinese citizens. The revealed facts of the research programs of Unit 731 are annually supplemented and made public by the Chinese side, films are released (the release of the work "731" is announced for July 2025), cultivating in the minds of the younger generation the prevention of a repetition of the past by curbing the spread of Japanese culture.

Keywords: China-Japan international relations, World War II, ethnic distance, post-conflict anxieties, Unit 731, biological laboratories.

Social conflicts remain omnipresent in modern societies. Although the causes of conflicts vary greatly, they are often determined by the presence of an ethnic component. This is even more pronounced in post-conflict societies, where inter-ethnic violence has severed ties between ethnic groups. A striking example is China and Japan. Years after the cessation of hostilities, the communities of these countries remain divided along ethnic lines. Despite existing attempts and initiatives for reconciliation to build peaceful development, the level of "ethnic distance" (as one of the most specific types of social distance) between the Chinese and the Japanese (previously involved in armed conflict), and the so-called "post-conflict anxieties" remain high. In the modern period, Beijing and Tokyo have failed to overcome inter-ethnic hostility, reduce ethnic distance and find a certain degree of coexistence.¹²

It has been 80 years, why can't the Chinese forget this ethnic hatred? According to statistics from World War II, the Chinese army suffered about 3.31 million casualties and 8.42 million innocent civilians. This is only the data from military records, not including the number of people who died from hunger, disease and cold. More than 200 million people across the country suffered the most severe hardships. Despite these figures, the main factor of "ethnic distance" and "post-

conflict anxiety" for the Chinese people remains the inhumane research activities of the Japanese Unit 731 during World War II.

Researchers continue to uncover new historical facts about the activities of the biological laboratories of this Unit. Created in 1935 by imperial decree, Unit 731 was a military bacteriological research unit of the Japanese army. The main goal of "Unit 731" was the creation of biological and chemical weapons. Under the leadership of General Shiro Ishii, methods of infecting with bubonic plague, cholera, plague, typhus and smallpox were developed.¹³ Experiments were carried out on people without anesthesia. The main goal was to use diseases as bacteriological weapons during World War II. Declassified materials obtained in 2025 indicate that one of the most common practices was ballistic tests to study the capabilities of Japanese weapons. During these exercises, prisoners were thrown with live grenades, fired at with flamethrowers, or even had bombs strapped to their bodies. As the charred remains of the victims fell to the ground, Japanese personnel diligently stood nearby, methodically recording the results.

It was common practice to expose Unit 731 prisoners to diseases so that the scientists present could monitor the progress of the disease. In even more gruesome experiments, organs were removed from perfectly healthy patients to see how long they could survive without them. Many prisoners were also subjected

¹² - Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies, Miha Šlebir, Rok Zupančič, Vol. 11, No. 2 (2024), pp. 211-229 (19 pages).

¹³ - Harris H. Sheldon, *Factories of Death: Japanese Biological Warfare, 1932-45, and the American Coverup*, (London: Routledge, First published 1994), 11. "Manchuria was used as a test site for national command planning by the bureaucrats... and a test site for the Continental Institute of Science which was established in 1935 at Harbin... as an experimental model of a science mobilization system that would never have been permitted in Japan proper. Professor Tsuneishi Kei-ichi

notes that "The scientists and technologists were better accommodated in Manchuria than in Japan with respect to availability of research funds and freedom to select research themes. Manchuria was probably a newly found paradise for these people. He concludes that in Manchuria, scientists and technologists were able to immerse themselves in research without frustration from shortage of funds and harassment from no specialist bureaucrats and others. There are those who believe that this was indeed the ideal environment for a scientific research system."

to forced limb amputations to collect data on the amount of blood lost. There were experiments using exposure to extreme cold to see how long the body could withstand before freezing to death.

Acting on orders from the Chief of the Army General Staff, Prince Kan'in Kotohito, through General Hajime Sugiyama or Yoshijiro Umezumi, the unit's activities were known to the government at the highest levels. Takahito Mikasa, Hirohito's younger brother, mentions it in his personal diary. Prince Tsuneyoshi Takeda, the Emperor's cousin, visited Unit 731's facilities on numerous occasions.¹⁴

The main research bases were located in northeastern China (Beiyinhe, Wuchang, Pingfang, and the vicinity of Harbin). The main subjects were Chinese, Koreans, and Russians, including women and children. As the empire expanded, more units were added to conquered cities such as Nanjing (Unit 1664), Beijing (Unit 1855), Qiqihar (Unit 516), Canton (Unit 8604), and Singapore (Unit 9420).¹⁵

Twenty-four documents written by key members of Unit 731 detailing the experimental work were collected in Japan. According to Yang Yan-jun, a junior researcher at the Unit 731 Research Center of the Harbin Academy of Social Sciences, the experiments on prisoners often went much further: living people were mummified, injected with horse blood, sometimes vivisection without anesthesia, prolonged exposure to X-rays or high atmospheric pressure. The "Japanese researchers" even practiced boiling while alive with interest.¹⁶ According to historians, about 300,000 people used as guinea pigs died during Unit 731's research.

Realizing defeat, on August 9, 1945, the Army General Staff in Tokyo ordered the destruction of the Pingfang Bacteriological Research Center. More than four hundred prisoners died from cyanide poisoning in food or were shot to ensure that no survivors could testify. The bodies were burned to erase all traces. Cyanide

was distributed to the remaining personnel (an estimated 1,200) with orders to commit suicide to avoid capture by the Soviets. On August 9 and 10, 1945, with the arrival of the Soviet army in Manchuria and Korea, the Japanese side, on the orders of their commander Sadayoshi Yamada, destroyed the archives. All detainees were killed, and 600 local Chinese workers were machine-gunned. Ishii gave a direct order to destroy all buildings before the arrival of the Russians.

However, in 1945, the Americans pressured the International Military Tribunal to act in the interests of the Japanese side. Ishii and his team were rescued in exchange for information and research, which was then used by the United States to develop its own biological weapons. Thus, the decision not to prosecute not only allowed Ishii and the others of Unit 731 to escape justice, but the resolution also encouraged the development of biological weapons.

The current generation of Japanese politicians resort to any forgery and trickery to absolve themselves of responsibility for the most brutal crimes of World War II. Tokyo seeks to reduce the "post-conflict anxiety" of the Chinese ethnic group through projects among the youth. It is worth noting that Washington and Tokyo have managed to completely eliminate the factors of "ethnic distance" and fully restore full-fledged international relations. However, Beijing defends the historical truth about World War II, continuing to cultivate the need to restore justice in relation to the most brutal studies of the Japanese army (in July 2025, Chinese cinema intends to release the film "731"). China's goal is to prevent a repetition of the mistakes of the past, including nationalism and fascism. As a result, the PRC continues to root the factors of "post-conflict anxiety" among the younger generation of the Chinese ethnic group, which in the long term will not allow moving to a new level of relations with Tokyo.

¹⁴ - <https://www.163.com/dy/article/JUFOTEER05563IC0.htm>

¹⁵ - Ishii led the development and application of biological weapons at Unit 731 in Manchuria during the Second Sino-Japanese War. At Unit 731, he engaged in forced human experimentation on civilians and prisoners of war that resulted in the death of over 10,000 people and was responsible for some of the most notorious war crimes of Imperial Japan. See Hal Gold, *Unit 731 Testimony*, 2003, 109. See also Barnaby

Wendy, *The Plague Makers: The Secret World of Biological Warfare*, (Frog Ltd., 1999).

¹⁶ - Article 171: The use of asphyxiating, poisonous or other gases and all analogous liquids, materials or devices being prohibited, their manufacture and importation are strictly forbidden in Germany. The same applies to materials specially intended for the manufacture, storage and use of the said products or devices. The manufacture and the importation into Germany of armored cars, tanks and all similar constructions suitable for use in war are also prohibited.